

Deliverable 4.1

Impact Assessment

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List of abbreviations

CAPs	Collective Awareness Platforms
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
WP	Workpackage
ZSI	Centre for Social Innovation – ZSI

Definition

Careables - an open solution that aims to improve the quality of life for people with unmet particular needs or facing physical limitations. Careables are often co-designed, replicable, accessible, adjustable and shareable online using digital technologies. Careables is a relatively new category, that promises more readily customized solutions and a more horizontal and collaborative approach to health and care.

1. Executive Summary

This deliverable describes Made4You's approach towards evaluation and impact assessment. Made4You facilitates the co-design of open healthcare for people with physical limitations and aims to unit a community of makers, health care professionals and people with physical limitations who develop and share a critical mass of careables (see definition above) that can be used and built upon, shared and documented on a knowledge-sharing platform. With this overarching aim we have formulated five objectives that relate to the accessibility and usefulness of the careables platform, the increased knowledge-sharing and cooperation amongst the stakeholders as well as the documentation and replication of careables.

With these project objectives as a starting point, this deliverable presents a methodology of how the project is evaluating its process and outcomes contributing to the achievement of these objectives. An integrated matrix of methods aligns the project objectives with specific evaluation questions, instruments for data gathering and impact indicators.

The presented approach towards evaluation and impact assessment is based on a literature review and theoretical assessment of how to evaluate participatory co-design projects and collective awareness platforms (CAPs). Given the heterogeneity of CAPs projects there is no single recipe for evaluation. In Made4You we put a special emphasis on *assessing the collaborative processes* involved in the co-design of open healthcare as well as the *potential of the developed careables platform*, designed for documentation and sharing of open healthcare solutions. A procedure on how to offer a proper description and documentation of the co-designed careables will be elaborated in workpackage 3. A project-internal evaluation of the developed careables is not foreseen, but those user who try to replicate, adapt or improve careables from the platform, are provided with the opportunity to share their feedback and experiences there. The analysis of this feedback will feed the impact assessment work of this workpackage.

Next to the overall evaluation and impact assessment strategy this deliverable includes a detailed description of the individual evaluation instruments together with a timeline to indicate the data collection phases. Potential risks and how these can be mitigated are likewise addressed. Following the guidelines of how to conduct responsible research and innovation (RRI) adherence to ethical guidelines that have been defined for the project in additional documents is obtained.

2. Introduction

The main objectives of workpackage 4 are to monitor the performance of the project, evaluate the expected outcomes and assess its potential impact. With this aim, data needs to be gathered that feed a set of monitoring criteria and impact metrics that have been developed in the initial stage of Made4You. For the appropriate data collection, a set of quantitative and qualitative data collection instruments have been elaborated which will help to evaluate the project's performance at different time-points of the project.

For the purpose of this deliverable and the work in WP4 we distinguish between evaluation and impact assessment. Our evaluation activities focus on development and implementation of the project. They include formative and summative aspects and are useful in determining whether certain activities should be continued, refined or determined and replaced with other activities. Impact assessment looks at the longer-term, deeper changes that have resulted from the project, including e.g. change in quality of life of the participants or changes in healthcare policies. While these aspects can often be measured only after the project end, we try to find evidence that indicates such changes to take place. In other words, evaluation data will help us to identify the strengths and weaknesses of the Made4You approach according to the initial goal set up by the project and to assess the potential impact of the project.

3. Objectives of evaluation and impact assessment

3.1. Overview

The main aim of evaluation and impact assessment is to ensure that the careables platform and the open personalized healthcare solutions are accurate and consistent with the planned objectives set out by the project and according to the real needs of the involved stakeholders – people with disabilities and citizens, makers, and health professionals. A second aim is to provide evidence for the envisioned impact and present ways to demonstrate the project's influence beyond the borders of the consortium. The project partners have an ambitious goal in terms of reaching out to a wide number of stakeholders and to make careables the preferred platform for open healthcare solutions.

These ambitious project goals also set a challenge for evaluation and impact assessment, especially for the latter, as long-term impact can only be measured after the official funding period has ended. In terms of evaluation we thus have to distinguish between formative evaluation and impact assessment:

- **Formative evaluation:** ensuring that the generated platform and provided documentation of the health care solutions are designed and implemented in a way

as to satisfy the requirements and needs of the involved stakeholders. The formative evaluation will assess user-acceptance factors, like ease of use and perceived usefulness, to allow an iterative improvement of both the platform and solutions. End-user input from the involved stakeholders will interactively shape the platform design documents and the health solutions themselves, trying to detect the non-conformances that may occur during the deployment of the careables approach as well as drivers for engagement and future wider usage.

- **Impact assessment:** evaluating the results in relation to the general objectives set up by the project and validate careables's impact within the involved communities and its potential impact beyond, such as the worldwide maker movement or open health initiatives. The assessment will provide insights into the benefits of our approach on an individual level as well as on the societal level of those communities involved.

Being aware that an impact assessment is not only critical for the project itself but, on a long-term perspective, also a key factor for the wider outreach of the careables approach, this WP also aims at the elaboration of a customized impact assessment model for the involved stakeholders. This assessment model will be based on the evaluation concept and its application within the project and be adapted to the means of the involved stakeholders. It will include selected indicators and provide guidelines and instruments on how to autonomously assess the impact of the careables approach after the deployment of the project.

As the project objectives have been defined very widely, a first ranking has taken place amongst the consortium member to help define the priorities of the evaluation team. The following list (Table 1:) shows the main five objectives as defined in the work programme of the project together with a ranking in terms of priority as defined collaboratively by the consortium partners. It also indicates some main implications for the evaluation of these objectives. It should be noted that while evaluation will consider all five objectives, the prioritization has been an important step in order to identify where the focus should be put.

Table 1: Overview of objectives and ranking of priority

Objectives	Implication for evaluation	Priority ranking
improve quality of life or services provided	The dimensions of "Quality of life" defined by different studies (e.g. Fitzpatrick et al. 1992; WHO); we can refer back to these studies and select the most suitable dimension for careables, also in alignment with the taxonomy/classification of careables. We will approach this topic mainly in a qualitative way.	5 (lowest)

establish collaboration between the communities	Quality of collaboration as defined by different studies; in the case of careables collaboration can take place and be evaluated in the co-design and local working sessions as well as in the online activities; thus, both aspects need to be considered, with a focus on the local collaboration in the Fablabs.	3
foster knowledge exchange	Knowledge exchange is closely related to and one of the regular outcomes of high quality collaborations. Potential effects of knowledge exchange are changes in knowledge/attitudes, practices and performance; all three aspects are relevant for the evaluation, as well as the a better understanding of effective knowledge exchange processes.	2
improve the accessibility of open source products	Accessibility of the platform and the open source products shared in the platform is increased if different target groups can better find, understand and communicate about careables. We will rely on existing criteria for accessibility, usability and usefulness and evaluate them with careables target users.	1 (highest)
allow anyone to replicate formats	Replication is closely connected to the aspect of accessibility and usability of the platform and the documentation process for careables. The evaluation of this objective will thus be aligned with the objective on accessibility.	4

Each of these objectives can be evaluated with a range of indicators in different breath and depth. In order to come up with a realistic and useful plan for evaluation we need to analyse existing concepts and methods that related to these objectives and combine the most relevant aspects for our purposes. In the following we briefly discuss current state-of-the-art of these approaches, concepts we can apply or adapt for our needs, and what it implies for the evaluation of the careables objectives.

3.2. Improve the accessibility of open sources products

Accessibility is very often related to the specific needs of people with disabilities that affect the use of online services and thus need to be considered when developing new platforms or services online.

“Accessibility addresses discriminatory aspects related to equivalent user experience for people with disabilities, including people with age-related impairments. For the web, accessibility means that people with disabilities can perceive, understand,

navigate, and interact with websites and tools, and that they can contribute equally without barriers.” (W3C Initiative)

The Web Accessibility Initiative (W3C) developed a set of guidelines with individuals and cooperations all around the world with the goal to share a single standard for web content accessibility. The Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG)¹ consist of 13 technical guidelines for web developers that contain testable success criteria for each of the guidelines.

In addition, the same initiative developed a set of Authoring Tool Accessibility Guidelines (ATAG)² that aim to make authoring tools themselves accessible, so that people with disability can create web content. Again, the guidelines are amended by a set of success criteria.

In Made4You accessibility for people with disabilities is key. Thus, both guidelines will be considered when developing the careables platform. Web accessibility will be tested using the suggested success criteria as well as by the involvement of people with disabilities in platform walkthrough.

In addition, we aim to support all representatives of our key target groups) – with disabilities and without – in:

finding

understanding

and using

careables information.

Therefore, the continuous assessment of usability and usefulness criteria of the platform is key:

“Usability and user experience design is about designing products to be effective, efficient, and satisfying. Specifically, ISO defines usability as the “extent to which a product can be used by specified users to achieve specified goals effectively, efficiently and with satisfaction in a specified context of use” (in [ISO 9241-11](#)). “The user experience is an extension of the usability concept and goes beyond reaching ones target efficiently, to integrate the emotional aspects when interacting with a product. „A person's perceptions and responses that result from the use and/or anticipated use of a product, system or service.” (in ISO 9241 - 210)

Indicators for usability are, for instance:

- Learnability,
- Efficiency (time to complete a task),
- Error rates,
- Satisfaction,

¹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG21/>

² <https://www.w3.org/WAI/standards-guidelines/atag/>

- Readability,
- Presentation of information,
- Incorporation of other media,
- Ease of navigation,
- Usefulness.

Indicators for user-experience are, for instance:

- Attractiveness,
- Stimulation,
- Novelty,
- Dependability

Usability and user experience can be evaluated in different phases of an iterative system design – from requirements collection to the post-implementation analysis. While the majority of health information systems engineering projects cover the post-implementation phase and only test the usability after a first implementation (see Table 2 below), we plan to cover the different phases with a set of analysis methods described further below.

Table 2 Percentages of selected studies per system design phase (from Peute et al. 2008)

System development phase	Perc. Usability studies	Applied Methods
Requirements phase	4%	Think Aloud , Interviews, User-requirements questionnaire
Specification/ development phase	19%	Heuristics, Cognitive Task Analysis, GOMMS
Implementation/ release phase	0%	-
Post-implementation analysis for insight into the need for system re-engineering or end-user satisfaction	73%	Surveys/ developed questionnaires, Cognitive Walkthrough, Logging and Observation of work practices, Heuristics, Think Aloud
Additional: system selection of commercially build system	4%	Comparative methods; survey/ requirement questionnaire

Assessing accessibility & usability & user experience in Made4You:

In Made4You usability and user experience will be continually assessed in strong cooperation with WP3, using the following phases (a more detailed description of the instruments applied in each phase can be found in the next chapter).

Requirement & specification development phase:

- “Walkthroughs”: representatives of the target groups are asked to walk through the first prototype, following specific tasks and providing their feedback during the process and afterwards. This approach will be performed at various stages of the

project, using iteratively better and higher-fidelity prototypes. First usability tests have already been conducted within the consortium and with representatives of the target groups. In addition, people with disabilities will specifically be invited to test the accessibility of careables applying the walkthrough technique.

- Usability questionnaires: Once the careables platform has reached a mature status, concerning functionality and designs, we will also distribute Usability questionnaires after the walkthroughs (SUS and AttrakDiff) to collect quantitative usability aspects.

Post implementation phase:

- “Walkthroughs”: Again we will ask representatives of our target groups to walkthrough the implemented platform, share their impressions with us and fill in a usability questionnaire.
- These data will be amended by usage statistics that show the acceptance of the platform.
- In addition, users will be provided with features to share their feedback and experiences with replicating, adapting, improving careables on the careables platform. The analysis of these feedbacks will be conducted continuously and fed back to the co-design teams. An integrated analysis of all feedbacks will provide insights on usefulness/usability of the careables themselves.

3.3. Knowledge exchange and quality of collaboration

Informal knowledge exchange in the careables co-design teams can be assessed in manifold ways. Fazey et al. (2014) report about four outcome dimensions typically found in the literature to assess knowledge exchange:

- changes in understanding, e.g. increased knowledge, change in attitudes, and changes in thinking
- changes in practice or policy
- improvements in business performance or human or ecological health
- Diversity of knowledge exchange processes; how knowledge exchange was conducted (patterns of interaction, involved learners etc.), quality of processes (e.g. levels of engagement, barriers)

Understanding the process is thereby equally important as the different effects of knowledge exchange. We thus consider these four dimensions as a good basis to assess the exchange of knowledge and experiences between people with special needs, their social networks, makers and health care professionals.

We understand these outcomes as one of the effects of an increased and effective collaboration between the stakeholders, which is another project goal, and will thus look at both aspects together.

Assessing the quality of collaboration can be done in different ways; an extensive concept was developed by Meier et al. (2007), who distinguish between nine dimensions to rate the

quality of collaborations. The following dimensions are rated on a five point Likert scale, where the rating is oriented by a training manual:

Communication

- Sustaining mutual understanding
- Dialogue management

Joint information processing

- Information pooling
- Reaching consensus

Coordination

- Task division
- Time management
- Technical coordination

Interpersonal relationship

- Reciprocal interaction

Motivation

- Individual task orientation

These dimensions were slightly adapted for different usages. They provide aspects that are very interesting to better understand 1) in how far the collaboration between the diversified target groups in Made4You could be established, and 2) what drivers and barriers were decisive in the co-design processes.

Assessing collaboration and knowledge exchange:

To assess the collaboration and knowledge exchange within the co-creation teams in Made4You, we will thus take input from the nine dimensions of collaboration (Meier et al. 2007) and the four dimensions of knowledge exchange evaluation (Frey et al. 2014), and develop the following instruments:

- **Live event evaluation cards and matrix:** the original set of event evaluation instruments will be extended to collect structured feedback from participants on collaboration and its' effect during local meet ups.
- **Question guidelines and exercises for a focus group:** we will invite two to three co-creation teams in each country to participate in a focus group together, to share their experiences on the collaboration and (learning) outcomes during the co-designing phase.
- **Platform usage statistics:** Only parts of the collaboration and knowledge exchange will take place on the online careables platform and the upcoming co-design sessions will show how many collaboration features we will add to platform. Depending on these features usage statistics will reveal more quantitative insights to the aspect of collaboration and knowledge exchange (e.g. nr. of comments shared with others, nr. of questions answered etc.) Together with the technical partner Wewolver we will develop indicators from the platform usage to assess the collaboration and knowledge exchange.

3.4. Replicability

Replicability of careables is supported if Made4you users can:

- Find full documentation of formats
- Exchange ideas/ask questions concerning formats
- Document replication of product or prototypes
- Improve and add to existing prototype documentation (both instructions, and documentation of research)

Assessment of replicability:

- Usability evaluation: In our understanding the replicability of careables is closely related to the usability of the careables platform and documentation, as well as the skill sets of involved participants. As we can not influence the skill set or at least this is not the aim of the project, we will take a close look at the documentations' usability and usefulness (see chapter 3.1)
- Platform usage statistics: The impact of the careables platform on replicability, especially the documentation of careables on this platform, can also be assessed via the usage statistics of the platform. Replicated "as is" without significant changes (i.e. bigger, or shorter, but without changing the shape) are counted. Modified careables are linked in the documentation (derivates or forked versions).

3.5. Improve the quality of life of people with special needs

The dimension of "Quality of life" are defined by different studies (e.g. Fitzpatrick et al. 1992; WHOQOL, 1995). Fitzpatrick et al. 1992 for instance defines six dimensions:

- physical functioning – for example, mobility, self-care
- emotional functioning – for example, depression, anxiety
- social functioning – for example, social support, social contact
- role performance – for example, work, housework
- pain
- other symptoms- for example, fatigue, nausea

The six quality of life dimensions defined by the WHO are quite similar and are (WHOQOL, 1995):

- Physical – for example, energy and fatigue, pain and discomfort
- Psychological – for example, negative and positive feelings, self-esteem
- Level of independence – for example, mobility, work capacity
- Social relationships – for example, social support, personal relationships
- Environment – for example, home environment, physical security
- Spirituality/Religion/Personal believes – for example, religion, spirituality

These different dimensions can be very interesting for Made4You to understand in how far the careables themselves, or the participation in the co-design processes, influenced the

quality of life of participants. We are aware of the fact that this is a huge concept that depends on many more aspects than just the involvement in Made4You, and that effects might even come with a certain time delay. Nevertheless we think that certain Made4You activities can have an influence on certain dimensions of quality of life. E.g. the participation in the co-design workshops could increase the social relationships or the emotional function (e.g. proud). A stomanoir (developed as a careable by Made4You) rather impacts physical functioning and might influence social and emotional aspects.

Assessing quality of life dimensions:

Lead user interviews: We will organize interviews with lead users, who were involved in the development process of careables to collect feedback on careables impact, as well as drivers and barriers experienced during the co-design process. When analyzing the interview results, the Quality of Life dimensions will serve us as codes to structure the mentioned impacts of Made4You. Interviews will be conducted at two time points, shortly after finishing the co-creation of a careable to collect feedback on the design-process and then after 2-3 months of using the careable to learn about the impact of the self-made health device on a people's life.

3.6. From Formative evaluation to impact assessment

As mentioned above, in our evaluation approach we distinguish between formative evaluation and impact assessment (including the summative evaluation). During the formative evaluation, which starts with the very first project activities, experiences are gathered and reflected in the consortium in order to make sure the processes are optimized and we learn from our mistakes and improve continuously.

During impact assessment, we aim to collect evidence for the impact that we are having on different levels mentioned above.

Figure 1: Overview of evaluation and impact assessment

As depicted in Figure 1 above, there are different data sources for evaluation and different stakeholders. The different data sources are analyzed and findings combined to get further insights.

4. Evaluation instruments

In this section we will introduce the evaluation instruments that will be applied to collect data for our evaluation and impact assessment. The evaluation instruments will collect data to evaluate the main project objectives from platform usage as well as the co-design events. An overview of all instruments can be seen in Table 3.

Table 3: Overview of evaluation instruments

Instruments	co-design events →			
	platform →	accessibility & usability/usefulness & replicability	knowledge exchange & quality of collaboration	impact & quality of life
walkthrough	✓			
scenario feedback cards	✓			
think aloud	✓			
focus group			✓	✓
questionnaire	✓		✓	✓
event feedback cards			✓	
event feedback poster			✓	
collaboration cards			✓	
usage statistics	✓		✓	
interviews	✓			✓
storytelling				✓

In the following chart (Figure 2) we have posed the instruments on a timeline. While the event evaluation will be conducted continuously, whenever MeetUps, conferences, presentations etc. are organized, the evaluation of co-design activities and impact of careables strongly depends on the continuous advancement of the co-design teams and will be flexibly adapted to their pace. The overview shows that the set of instruments will feed the project on a continuous basis with evaluation data, which will be reflected upon in bi-weekly self-reflection meetings and in two self-assessment occasions, as well as analyzed and documented in the two upcoming Deliverables D4.2. and D4.3.

Figure 2: Timeline of evaluation activities

4.1. Event evaluation

In Made4You a series of different event formats have been planned, gradually increasing the level of engagement for the participants and contributing to community building. There are thus events planned that start with the aim of raising awareness for the topic to workshop series that engage makers, patients and healthcare professionals in co-design sessions that can span across a few weeks or even months. Also, the Fablabs are exploring in terms of workshop formats to find the most suitable ways in engaging the local stakeholders.

Thus, we are faced with a rather big variety of event formats and evaluation has to adapt to this broad range with a set of evaluation instruments that can be adapted to the local needs of the event. The instruments range from the classical feedback questionnaire to more informal postcards or the collection of quick feedback via posters and oral feedback rounds.

These instruments can collect formative feedback on the events themselves and first effects like increased interest or the motivation to engage in open healthcare and talk about it with others (see Figure 3, 4 and 5).

CAREABLES
TITLE of event
Place, Date, Moderator

Please take 2 minutes to evaluate today's event. ☺ Thank you!

⊕

	Does not apply at all	Applies fully
The objectives were clear and comprehensible.	0 1 2 3 4 5 6	
Practical knowledge was provided.	0 1 2 3 4 5 6	
A good understanding of contexts was provided.	0 1 2 3 4 5 6	
The aim was clearly communicated.	0 1 2 3 4 5 6	
There was enough room for my questions and interests.	0 1 2 3 4 5 6	
The time allotted was utilized/filled in an optimal way.	0 1 2 3 4 5 6	
There was enough time for reflection and experience exchange with others.	0 1 2 3 4 5 6	
My own involvement (e.g. interest, preparation, concentrated attention, cooperation, etc.) in the event was intensive.	0 1 2 3 4 5 6	
I have achieved something important through this event.	0 1 2 3 4 5 6	
Altogether this event was worth taking place.	0 1 2 3 4 5 6	

events evaluation 1

What did you like best?

What could be improved?

Any other comments?

What is your profile?

healthcare user maker healthcare professional
 family member interested citizen policy maker
 other:

events evaluation 2

Figure 3: Feedback questionnaire

we appreciate your feedback!

CAREABLES

How was today's event for you?

- The event was very relevant for me ☆☆☆☆☆
- The event raised my interest ☆☆☆☆☆
- The event was well organised ☆☆☆☆☆
- I will inform others about it ☆☆☆☆☆
- The event motivated me to engage in open healthcare ☆☆☆☆☆

I would like to be informed about future CAREABLES activities; please contact me via: _____
(e-mail)

Figure 4: feedback postcards

Figure 5: Feedback posters

But the instruments can also specifically address aspects of collaboration and knowledge exchange, especially in those events, where co-design teams meet for the co-creation of careables.

Event collaboration cards (see Figure 6) can contain the following items:

Collaboration in your co-creation team (please rate from “totally agree” – to “totally disagree”, 5 point likert scale):

- Although we all speak our own speech and come from different worlds, we learn to better understand each other (mutual understanding)
- We collect as many solution-relevant pieces as possible, everybody brings in his/her expertise (information pooling).
- We critically discuss alternatives on our way and reach agreement on important decisions (consensus reaching).
- We split tasks between us and take one step after the other with a clear goal in mind (task division).
- We treat each other with respect and encourage one another to contribute opinions and perspectives (reciprocal interaction).
- Every team-members actively engages in finding a good solution to the problem, thus bringing his or her knowledge and skills to bear (individual task orientation).

Knowledge exchange:

- Is there anything new that you learned today?
- What helps you to learn in this co-creation process?

The Collaboration card is a tool for assessing collaboration quality. It features a title 'Collaboration card' with a circular icon of three people and the Careables logo. Below the title is a list of six statements, each followed by a five-point Likert scale. The scale is labeled 'We totally disagree' on the left and 'We totally agree' on the right, with five stars in between.

	We totally disagree					We totally agree
◆ Although we all speak our own speech and come from different worlds, we learn to better understand each other .	☆	☆	☆	☆	☆	
◆ We collect as many solution-relevant pieces as possible, everybody brings in his/her expertise.	☆	☆	☆	☆	☆	
◆ We critically discuss alternatives on our way and reach agreement on important decisions.	☆	☆	☆	☆	☆	
◆ We split tasks between us and take one step after the other with a clear goal in mind.	☆	☆	☆	☆	☆	
◆ We treat each other with respect and encourage one another to contribute opinions and perspectives.	☆	☆	☆	☆	☆	
◆ Every team-members actively engages in finding a good solution to the problem, thus bringing his or her knowledge and skills to bear.	☆	☆	☆	☆	☆	

Figure 6: Collaboration card to assess the collaboration quality between careables co-creators

In addition, partners are reporting their experiences from the events in a detailed reporting file, where they also provide information on the type of event, the type of audience attending, or specific details about the activities carried out during the event.

4.2. Careables platform evaluation

The careables platform is a core element of the whole project and one of the most important outcomes in terms of sustainability. It is thus a core source of data gathering from an evaluation perspective. Apart from extracting data from its usage to assess the objective defined above and serving as a data source, there are additional means to assess the quality of the platform. The following instruments will be applied:

4.2.1. Co-design sessions

Co-design is a core element of the whole project design in careables. The nature of co-design is to involve end-users, researchers and designers creatively from the very beginning, so that they, jointly articulate ideas, experiment with concepts, make and evaluate sketches, and tinker with mock-ups or prototypes. Key ideas behind co-design are that everyday people can and should become participants and co-creators, rather than customers and users (Sanders et al. 2008), and that end-users can contribute as experts of their experiences to research and design processes.

Thus, at the same time as being an important design instrument, co-design is also an important means for formative evaluation, as with this method we are gathering feedback about the platform from the very beginning from users. The feedback will be collected in co-design sessions via different means (flashcards, flipcharts, etc.) and documented for further input of the different working teams, especially workpackage 3.

Figure 7: Example of co-design session

4.2.2. Usability and user experience workshops

In Made4You we will apply **walkthroughs** through running prototypes with representatives from our target groups to get feedback on usability and user-experience. The Walkthrough technique derives from the Cognitive Walkthrough method (Wharton, Rieman et al. 1994), a usability inspection method that focuses on evaluating a design particularly by exploration. The focus of this technique is motivated by the observation that many users prefer to learn software by exploration, instead of investing time for comprehensive formal training. In a Cognitive Walkthrough, a group of designers or software experts tries to take the viewpoint of their target user population and evaluates a proposed interface in the context of one or more specific user tasks.

This procedure uncovers implicit or explicit assumptions made by developers about users' knowledge of the task and the interface conventions. It helps to find mismatches between users' and designers' conceptualization of a task, as well as poor choices of wording for menu titles and button labels, and inadequate feedback about the consequences of an action (Wharton, Rieman et al. 1994).

Nevertheless one of the critics of the Cognitive Walkthrough technique is that the method is based on the designers' assumptions about the end-users' behaviour and knowledge.

Thus the project took the decision to ask our end-users to participate in Walkthroughs through the careables platform, using predefined tasks that cover the main functions of the applications. The aim of these Walkthroughs is to find usability issues and assess the

learnability for our target group. In addition, we aim to provide the end-users with hands-on sessions to enrich later discussions about the perceived usefulness of the application, as well as barriers of the features and functionalities provided.

To deal with task variability and alternate courses of actions, tasks are modeled as a set of likely alternate paths for achieving an intended outcome, focusing on the users' experiences with the interface while carrying out tasks, and the interface's support for helping the user to fulfill the intended outcome (Pinchelle and Gutwin 2002).

To understand the users' reasoning of action we combine the Walkthrough with **Think-aloud tests** and embed the tasks within **scenarios**, which are very much tied to practical concerns and common situations of our target group. An example for a scenario proposed to a user during a walkthrough I seen in Figure 8.

SCENARIO 1

Searching for a careable

- Imagine you are a potential careables user, who is using a **wheelchair**.
- You want to see if there is something interesting for you on the careables platform, without having something specific in mind.

- *How would you proceed? What would you do on the careables platform?*

Figure 8: Scenario card that gives test users tasks in the careable platform

To allow documentation of the collected experiences from the Walkthroughs we provide **Feedback-Cards** (see Figure 9) where, after each task, end-users evaluate the task's difficulty and attractiveness, and note suggestions for improvement for the later discussion.

Scenario - FEEDBACK CARD

How did you feel, when trying out the suggested scenario on the careables platform?
(Please tick the most appropriate symbol)

😄 😊 😐 😞 😡

How difficult or easy was it for you to successfully solve the suggested scenario?
(Please tick the most appropriate box)

Very difficult Very easy

How satisfied are you with the features that the careables platform offered you to solve the suggested scenario?

Very unsatisfied Very satisfied

How would you rate the time that you needed to solve the suggested scenario?

Needed too much time Needed only a short time

Figure 9 Scenario Feedback Card

Immediately after the Walkthroughs each participant is requested to complete an evaluation questionnaire (see next point).

4.2.3. Usability and user-experience evaluation questionnaires

To test aspects of usability and user-experience several questionnaires have been developed to easily and systematically collect an end-users feedback on new products. These questionnaires have slightly different foci and have been analysed by Schrepp et al. (2016). A questionnaire that serves the purpose to get a quick insight into most important user-experience aspects is the System Usability Scale (SUS) (Lewis and Sauro, 2009). In the SUS participants are asked to score the following 10 items with one of five responses that range from “strongly Agree” to “strongly disagree”:

- I think that I would like to use this system frequently.
- I found the system unnecessarily complex.
- I thought the system was easy to use.
- I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system.
- I found the various functions in this system were well integrated.
- I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system.
- I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly.
- I found the system very cumbersome to use.
- I felt very confident using the system.
- I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system.

In addition, the SUS could be complemented by a questionnaire that focuses more on emotional aspects of user experience, like the AttrakDiff instrument (Hassenzahl et al. 2003) – see also Figure 10. It consists of 28 items whose poles are opposite adjectives (e.g. "confusing - clear", "unusual - ordinary", "good - bad") and users have to decide between seven steps between those opposite adjectives. Each set of adjective items is ordered into a scale of intensity (see Figure 9). Each of the middle values of an item group creates a scale value for pragmatic quality (PQ), hedonic Quality (HQ) and attractiveness (ATT).

Please click one item in every line.

human*	<input type="radio"/>	technical						
isolating*	<input type="radio"/>	connective						
pleasant*	<input type="radio"/>	unpleasant						
inventive*	<input type="radio"/>	conventional						
simple*	<input type="radio"/>	complicated						
professional*	<input type="radio"/>	unprofessional						
ugly*	<input type="radio"/>	attractive						
practical*	<input type="radio"/>	impractical						
likeable*	<input type="radio"/>	disagreeable						
cumbersome*	<input type="radio"/>	straightforward						

Figure 10: AttrakDiff indicators to collect feedback on the user-experience of the careables platform

4.2.4. Platform usage data

A very common means of getting usage data is the automatic data extraction from the platform. The data that can typically be extracted and may give insights for the evaluation of the platform usage is, e.g.:

- Nr. of users
- Nr. of visits
- Nr. of sites visited
- Session duration
- No. of returning visitors
- Nr. of documents downloads
- Nr. of careables created, adapted, replicated.
- No. of comments
- No. of questions/contacts with editors
- Nr. of editors
- Nr. of careables edited
- Most interesting sites
- Sites spent most time with
- Careables with most comments

This list of usage data will be continually extended when features for collaboration and knowledge exchange will be added to the careables platform. Then we will be able to better

understand how the collaboration between our target users on the platform itself is taking place.

4.2.5. Survey on the platform

Finally, once the platform has a certain critical mass of users, online surveys and polls that can be directly integrated in the platform may be a good means for gathering feedback on a more quantitative level.

Online surveys, whether for the platform evaluation or any other type of data gathering purpose, will be based on LimeSurvey, a survey tool that is running on the ZSI server, allowing for complete data protection at any time.

This is currently an option that will be further explored during the course of the project.

4.3. Personal and social impact assessment

4.3.1. Focus groups with co-design teams

Focus groups are, next to interviews, a very common means to gather qualitative research data. They are a type of group interview with the advantage to get a common understanding between participants, compared to the individual views obtained via interviews. In addition, the group interaction during the process may trigger participants to come up with additional associations they would not have thought in the first place and would not have mentioned in a personal interview.

The focus groups can be arranged to give alternatively individual and group tasks to give every participant the chance to share experiences. A good number for focus groups is 7-12 participants and the questions to be addressed in an individual focus group setting should not be more than 5 to 7. In the case of the focus groups for this project we plan to set the main focus on the collaboration in co-design teams and the impact of this collaboration (e.g. knowledge exchange, quality of life dimensions).

As focus groups will be locally conducted partners of the consortium will be trained to perform focus groups with their co-design participants in their language and adapted to their specific engagement in the project.

4.3.2. Interviews

In order to gather feedback on the personal impact we envision interviews (see above) to be another appropriate instrument.

In social sciences there are a number of different interviewing techniques, ranging from very open to very structured ways of communication. In the case of careables we are planning to apply mostly semi-structured interviews, which follow the problem-centred interview approach (Witzel, 2000). Methodologically the concept of problem-centred interviews

„borrows largely from the theory-generating procedure of grounded theory (Glaser & Strauss, 1998), but the insight gained through data collection and evaluation must rather be organized as an inductive-deductive mutual relationship.” (cited from Witzel, 2000) in order to gain also an understanding of the specific user needs and expectations according to their very personal situations.

The main instrument of the problem-centered interviews is a question guideline, which covers the main aspects of open healthcare. This guideline supports the interviewer's memory on the topics of research and provides a framework of orientation to ensure comparability of interviews. It includes ideas for lead questions into individual topics and pre-formulated questions to start the discussion. These initial questions are broadly formulated and function “like an empty page which is filled out by the interviewee in his or her own words, structured in his or her own way” (Witzel, 2000). In the continued progress of communication, the interviewer can ask questions which reveal further details of sequences offered by the respondent, investigating concrete examples of experiences or biographical episodes. Ad-hoc questions are posed when certain topics of the question guidelines are left out and are needed to secure the comparability of the interviews. To gain insights into the personal impact of the overall project on the lives of people, these interviews will give specifically room for ad-hoc personal reflections.

The interviews will be tape-recorded for later transcription, if agreed upon by the interviewee. If interviews are recorded, the interviewee will need to approve the script. In both cases, if recording permission is granted or not, interviewers will elaborate postscripts directly after the interview, keeping records of the topics discussed, comments on situative and non-verbal aspects of the interview as well as topics and ideas which are suggestions for later interpretations. If interviews are not recorded, interviewers will take notes and prepare detailed protocols to replace the transcript.

For the analysis of the interviews, the research team will conduct qualitative content analysis of the transcripts as proposed by Mayring (2000). The basis of the analysis are cases: the complete transcripts of the interviews, a case description or biographical data which can be added, and the records of the interviewer. The applied method is a technique of summarisation, whereby categories are created in an inductive procedure by reducing, paraphrasing and generalising relevant text passages using a software like MAXQDA3. The central aspect of the employed technique is to develop categories as close as possible resembling the original data without formulating theories or concepts in advance.

The analysis will be conducted in three steps: 1) Summarisation, 2) Explication and 3) Structuring. Systematic contrasting of cases, aiming to find similarities and differences amongst cases, will follow the development of case-specific main topics. At least two researchers will be involved in the analysis of every transcript. Only those categories and respective sub-categories, which all agreed upon will be introduced or retained. This method of co-analysis guarantees improvements of objectivity. The results do not depend on one specific person and are reproducible independently of the individual researcher. As

anonymity is guaranteed to the participants, each interviewee will be given a unique code instead of revealing their names. The findings consist of a systematisation of the relevance of codes, a generalisation and an interpretative framework. They will help to identify aspects of personal impact of careables on the quality of lives of the individuals.

4.3.3. Storytelling

Another qualitative approach that we will apply for impact assessment is the method of storytelling, which is also considered a generative tool for co-design that captures participants' self-expression (Sanders, 2000). Storytelling is part of the narrative genre and for the purpose of this research we will not draw a strict line between storytelling and narratives, as the important aspect is to show impact on the personal lives of people, and not to contribute to a methodological discussion.

4.4. Project self-assessment

In addition to the evaluation instruments described above, which collect input from those external stakeholders involved in the co-creation of careables, the Made4You consortium will conduct two (project-internal) self-assessment exercises: a project-mid-term self-assessment, and a final project self-assessment. These will be critical reflection exercises of the whole consortium in an online meeting. The basis for the self-assessment will be an adaptation of the citizen science evaluation framework (Kieslinger et al. 2017). This framework consists of a set of questions relating to 1) the process and 2) the impact of projects, looking into three dimensions: a) scientific, b) involvement of citizens, c) broader impact on society, environment and economy. As the framework was created to assess citizen science projects, it will be adapted for the self-assessment of DIY health care projects in WP4.

The self-assessment will help us to make our strengths evident and to see our shortcomings and supports the project management in guiding the project towards achieving its goals.

5. Initial insights from formative evaluation in 1st year

5.1. Insights from events evaluation

During the regular online meetings of the consortium we are continuously exchanging and reflecting about the different experiences of the partners with the events. In addition, there is a more formal way of documenting the experiences in a shared monitoring file. In each of the three maker spaces, Milano, Amsterdam and Berlin, a series of workshops and MeetUps have taken place. The aim of these events was to address the target audiences and make them stepwise more engaged in the project, leading to co-designed careables products.

During the first year, each partner organization chose a slightly different strategy for their engagement strategy in order to test different approaches and learn from the experiences (a

more detailed elaboration on the organized workshops can be found in D1.1). The workshops that had the most fruitful results were conducted in Amsterdam. Various reasons contribute to this success, amongst others the fact that WAAG worked with a hospital and had support from in-house makers working with healthcare professionals and people with specific needs.

In Milano, the engagement of the people with needs attending the MeetUps has been growing during the first year, but the attendance of the makers was going down. An important learning in this maker space has been evolved around the fact about how to motivate more people with engineering and maker skills. Sponsoring some projects, giving the makers more visibility or even working with some other reward system might be needed to compensate for the makers' effort that they put into the co-design of a careable.

In Berlin, the idea was to focus on one specific disability challenge in each of the MeetUp sessions. In addition, in order to speed up the process the Berlin FabLab was experimenting with rapid prototyping and offering professional support. It was also a learning that the term "MeetUp" raises different expectations, where people do not expect to get involved in a longer co-design process. After some recent changes in the organizational structures of the FabLab Berlin, the new organization is planning to promote careables MeetUps as learning opportunities, such as training in co-designing, design thinking, rapid prototyping, etc. This offers people the additional educational benefit and we expect to raise interest and achieve higher attendance especially amongst makers.

The summary of the experiences and lessons learned from the three spaces are reported in D1.2 and will be prepared as "how-to" guidelines to share with other maker spaces.

5.2. Insights from the platform design

First insights for the platform design were collected during several occasions.

Three different questionnaires, which were sent out to makers, health care professionals and people with special needs, collected input on requirements for the careables platform from our main target groups. The main results from the analysis of these questionnaires can be found in D3.1.

During co-design sessions in the Netherlands, where users already started to document their careables on the platform, important initial formative evaluation data has been collected on the documentation process and the supportive function of the platform.

During the MakeHealth event in Eindhoven walk-through sessions were organized with partners from the consortium as well as external target group members. The sessions were concentrating on testing the documentation tool for careables, but test users were also providing very valuable feedback about the overall platform experience, e.g. the registration process or the account management.

All the collected information is shared in the consortium in a document and discussed during the weekly online meetings. Issues reported by the test users related to very specific details

of the documentation tool, such as the uploading or downloading of files, making subfolders, tagging, etc. Overall, an important feedback was also that the current status of the platform is not very easy for novices to be used and the workflow on the platform has to be eased and offer a more self-explanatory approach towards sharing careables.

The detailed feedback has been taken up in workpackage 3, is documented in deliverable D3.1 and will be reflected in the next version of the careables platform.

6. Risks and contingencies

While risk monitoring is part of the continuous monitoring process performed by the project management there are also a few risks that should be mentioned in the context of evaluation and impact assessment. In the following we will discuss the main potential risks for evaluation identified so far and propose actions to be taken to cope with each specific risk.

Co-design

- There is the risk related to co-design and that this might drive the project away from its original objectives. There might be discrepancies between the priorities of the consortium and the priorities of target stakeholders. We also might be confronted with too high expectations towards what a careable could be, in contrast to what can be realized by the DIY-approach.

Action:

- To address this risk the organizers of the Made4You MeetUps will specifically take care to moderate and balance upcoming expectations with regard to their technically feasible implementation. Best practices will be exchanged between the organisers of MeetUps in the three countries and documented in our reports.

Number of participants:

- We do not achieve the required number of volunteers to get involved in the building and documentation of careables. Thus, the impact measurement would be limited to a small number of people and the impact as such would be smaller than expected, as a limited number of careables would also make the careables platform less attractive.

Action:

- To address the risk of having lower number of participants we will carefully monitor the number of target users who show interest in our project, share good and bad experiences from the involvement and communication process amongst consortium partners. If we observe low interest in selected areas or amongst selected target groups (e.g. makers), we will elaborate additional incentives for participation, think about additional target groups that might be attracted by our ideas and share all lessons learned within the consortium as well as in our reports. In addition, we develop a tool that is seen as a free resource to others, so we are adding value to others lives if people commit to our philosophy and tool. This value will be actively communicated to all

stakeholder groups.

Technical problems

Risk:

- The technological infrastructure does not work as expected: We develop technically complex systems and especially the documentation of careables is a challenging task. But the success of the target users' involvement depends on a running platform and documentation authoring tool, as well as useful careables.

Action:

- The CAPTOR consortium has foreseen an iterative implementation and testing of its technical infrastructure. Throughout the whole development and roll-out we will stay in close contact with our target users, evaluation activities have a strong focus on the continuous formative evaluation which is fed back to the development team. In addition, developers will participate in workshops with target users on usability/user-experience/accessibility to grasp and understand the difficulties of users who interact with our platform and documentation tool.

Language barriers

- Local MeetUps and co-creation process take place and are supported in the participants' mother tongue. The careables themselves should be available to a large audience, so how should careables descriptions and documentation be accessible in a high number of languages?

Action:

- The documentation of careables is done in mother tongue of the careables creators and a translation tool like Google translator will allow to translate it to other languages like English. This initial translation can then be edited. So each careable is available at least in two languages – the creators mother tongue and a basic English version.

7. Ethics

Personal data will be collected from participants during interviews, focus groups and discussions following the walkthroughs.

Thus, we have created informed consents for the specific target groups, e.g. adults, parents, and children that will be distributed to those involved in the evaluation activities. More details on our ethical approach and instruments can be found in deliverable D8.1 and D8.2 as well as the handbook.

8. Conclusion and outlook

The experiences of the first year have already delivered important feedback for the formative evaluation, of the co-design process as well as the platform design. Most importantly the consortium has established a trusted working environment where all partners exchange feedback and critically reflect on the experiences. The different approaches towards organizing engagement events in the maker spaces have clearly pointed us towards critical points that need to be addressed in the future. Especially stakeholder engagement for a longer period during the co-design is a challenge. Incentive models are currently being elaborated and tested in the different spaces.

In terms of the platform the co-design sessions with direct feedback from the target groups have been taken up by the design and development team and will be realized in a stepwise approach in the next versions of the platform, with a prioritization of the most relevant features. Continuous user feedback will feed into further iterations of the platform.

In addition to the presented instruments the Advisory Board members will be involved in reflective feedback sessions to contribute with their expertise on the future orientation of the project.

Finally from a purely evaluation and impact assessment view, we will be gradually moving from the ongoing formative evaluation towards impact assessment. While the second year of the project will still be characterized as a learning journey of the consortium and rely heavily on formative feedback, in the third year we plan to move towards drawing conclusions and feed them into a sustainable model for the careables platform and open healthcare solutions.

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